

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.17 Report from the first webinar

Public

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1. Summary

This document is a part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). The goal of the deliverable D6.17 “Report from the first webinar” is to report on the 1st CYCLOPES webinar as a dissemination event, which was held online on May 24th 2022. This 1st webinar is the first annual webinar and part of task 6.4. This task manages the webinars that will be used to provide an additional option to engage stakeholders within the cybercrime community. The topic for this 1st webinar, ‘Social Engineering’ has been chosen by the coordinator in collaboration with work package leaders from WP2, 3 and 5.

Furthermore, the webinar sessions will run annually and will be organised in cooperation with partner networks established through WP5, in an effort to maximise reach and impact and to amplify participation.

2. Introduction

The project dissemination activities in general and the webinars in particular, are mainly construed as CYCLOPES Community networking events and focus on sharing the results among the identified and newly identified community members and stakeholders and other relevant audience of interest.

The webinar’s methodology will form a model for a delivery, that is repeatable and scalable. Although, the delivery, the audience size and the feedback from attendees will be assessed following each iteration. This procedure will allow the team working in T6.4 to provide a better experience for the registrants of the webinars in each new edition. The webinars are used to complement the activities of WP2 and WP3; hence, they will be used to conclude earlier discussions or to trigger new topical areas that will be further reviewed. For the first webinar the topic of ‘Social Engineering’ was chosen to build on the results of the 3rd CYCLOPES workshop on that topic.

The CYCLOPES Community members and stakeholders audience are at the core of the main goals of the CYCLOPES Communication and Dissemination Plan. Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient community members relations in order to enable interaction between differing innovation parties, and build synergies with already established European, national and sub-national networks of practitioners.

3. 1st CYCLOPES Webinar

3.1. Main goal and set-up of the webinar

Efficient dissemination during the CYCLOPES project ensures short and long-term successes of the project. Within any project, the dissemination is a fundamental activity to create project visibility and reach various target groups. Through yearly Webinar Events, CYCLOPES would like to ensure that:

- Project outputs and outcomes are widely disseminated to the right target audiences. Since the CYCLOPES workshops and Joint Live Exercises (WP2 and 3) are for practitioners only, the annual webinars (and dissemination events) are ideal to reach out to a wider audience;
- CYCLOPES community members and stakeholders are encouraged to contribute to the CYCLOPES outputs development, evaluation and exploitation. Thus, they should be identified and encouraged from the start to proactively interact with the consortium partners.

A crucial part of webinar events is to complement the activities of WP2, WP3 and WP4; hence, they can be used to conclude earlier discussions or trigger new topical areas that will be further reviewed. These webinar events foster additional network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners and stakeholders who may wish to join to the CYCLOPES network and its activities.

3.2. Program of the webinar

On the 24th of May 2022, the 1st CYCLOPES webinar was held online using Zoom Webinar. The event was organised and hosted by the Dutch Institute for Technology, Safety and Security (DITSS). The audience was made up of around 45 participants from LEAs across Europe.

The announcement, including the final program and registration detailed, was organised as follows:

1st CYCLOPES Webinar

Social Engineering aspect of Cybercrimes affecting People 24th May 2022 ; 10-12.00h CET

I. Introduction

1. Although most cybercrime will result in a technical exploitation of a computer or a network, the most common route into a victim's system is through social engineering rather than a technical attack. Advances in cyber security are hardening networks to make 'Brute Force' attacks far more difficult, and with end to end encryption becoming the default for most communications, social engineering gives the criminal the greatest opportunity for system compromise.
2. This webinar will discuss and share the results of the CYCLOPES workshop on Social Engineering (30/31 March 2022 in Stockholm)
3. Best practices by a European LEA organisation

II. AUDIENCE / TARGET GROUP

European Law Enforcement Agencies, Research organisations and Industry/SMEs active in fighting cybercrime.

Number of participants: around 50 people

III. AGENDA

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| 10:00 – 10:05 | Welcome/Opening; <i>Peter van de Crommert, CYCLOPES Community Manager</i> |
| 10:05 – 10:15 | Introduction to the CYCLOPES Network
<i>Rashel Talukder, PPHS; CYCLOPES Project Coordinator</i> |
| 10:15 – 10:45 | Social Engineering: the People aspect at a glance
<i>Ignas Melman and Hugo Bijmans, TNO</i> |

- 10:45 – 11:15 CYCLOPES Workshop sharing results on Social Engineering topic:
Meera Barnett, Home Office
- 11:15 – 11:45 Best practice from a LEA practitioner
Louise Gibson, Leicester Police, UK
- 11:45 – 12:00 Open Discussion and closing the event
Peter van de Crommert, DITSS; CYCLOPES Community Manager

IV. Registration and weblink

Please register to this event via:

<https://forms.office.com/r/6JH2ZvJmbK>

For registration a Microsoft form was used:

CYCLOPES Social Engineering Webinar Registration
24th of May - 10:00 - 12:00 CET

* Vereist

Privacy policy

By applying, I consent to participate in the CYCLOPES (grant agreement no 101021669) event and agree that the personal data about me which is gathered in the course of and as the result of my participation in this event will be (i) collected and retained for the purpose of this project and (ii) accessed and analysed by the researchers for the purpose of conducting this project.

All data will be managed in accordance with the project's Privacy Policy, available here:
<https://cyclopes-project.eu/privacy-policy>

1. I have read, understood and agree to the Privacy Policy of the Cyclopes Community *

Yes

No

Volgende

3.3. Results of the event

Although we had a rather short timeframe between the webinar announcement and the actual webinar event (3-4 weeks) our promotion activities (inviting the CYCLOPES Community directly, messages on social media, using partners networks) the event had 46 registered participants from the following different organisation types:

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● EU LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENC...	21
● INDUSTRY / SMES	2
● ACADEMIC RESEARCH	11
● JUDICIAL EXPERTS	0
● GOVERNMENTS/PUBLIC BODIES	1
● CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS	0
● CYBERCRIME NETWORKS AND ...	3
● Andere	8

The registrations came from 17 different countries.

With respect to the community building and communication goals the webinar also enriched the CYCLOPES community by 35 registrants that wanted to join the CYCLOPES community and 38 that wanted to receive our newsletter:

Would you like to join the Cyclopes Community?

● Yes	35
● No	9
● Maybe	2

Would you like to receive our newsletter?

● Yes	38
● No	8
● Maybe	0

The following key points from the feedback and discussion have been identified:

- 1) Fighting Cybercrime in general and Social Engineering in particular would largely benefit from more focus on 'Cyber Prevent' activities.
- 2) CYCLOPES can form a good bridge between European LEAs, RTOs and companies.
- 3) Using the CYCLOPES Webinars as an extension of a Practitioners workshop theme to involve not only practitioners, but also other flavours of CYCLOPES community members/stakeholders is a good approach to enrich the discussion and solution thinking.
- 4) When the participants were asked what should be prioritised by practitioners fighting cybercrime, we received the following feedback:
 - Criminal groups targeting (small) organisations (without means for excellent cyber protection) in particular the ones that can have high impacts for the citizen: hospitals, local administrations or smaller / local utility companies;
 - Fake news, ransomware;
 - Offender prevention;
 - Cryptography, AI and Threat Hunting methodology;
 - On a national / international scale: Cybersecurity (Ransomware); On a local scale: "small" cybercrime: phishing / extortion of individuals that became a multi-million dollar industry since Covid-19;
 - Deepfakes and synthetic media in relation to social engineering;
 - Fighting fake news and fake facts dispersed on the web.
- 5) The results of this 1st CYCLOPES webinar event are very valuable for future CYCLOPES activities.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable summarises the 1st CYCLOPES webinar event. It was used to provide an additional opportunity to engage stakeholders within the cybercrime community.

Although most cybercrime will result in a technical exploitation of a computer or a network, the most common modus operandi (or better said, modus via) into a victim's system is through social engineering, rather than through a technical attack. Advances in cyber security are hardening networks to make 'Brute Force' attacks far more difficult, and with end to end encryption becoming the default for most communications, social engineering gives the criminal the greatest opportunity for system compromise.

This webinar discussed and shared the results of the CYCLOPES workshop on Social Engineering (which was held on 30/31 March 2022 in Stockholm) including some best practices by a European LEA organisations.

With 46 registrants from 17 different countries, it is safe to say that the event was a success, sharing insightful and clear presentations. During the productive discussion session, all participants were able to input their thoughts and opinions in relevant matters regarding Social Engineering, especially those regarding Cyber Prevent, possible solution and ongoing research. The 2nd CYCLOPES Webinar Event will be planned for first half of 2023.

Annex 1st CYCLOPES Webinar presentations

Opening/Welcome:

Agenda

Social Engineering aspect of Cybercrimes affecting People

1st CYCLOPES Webinar, 24th May 2022, online

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101021669

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Social Engineering: the People aspect at a glance;

TNO innovation for life

SOCIAL ENGINEERING CYCLOPES WEBINAR

Ignas Melman & Hugo Bijmans, TNO

INTRODUCTION DEFINITION AND CONTEXT

Definition: Social engineering is a manipulation technique that exploits human error to gain private information, access, or valuables.

Generally used for two goals:

1. Theft: Obtaining valuables like information, access, or money
2. Sabotage: Disrupting or corrupting data to cause harm or inconvenience.

Stepping stone systems: for a variety of attacks; social engineering is often used as a first step in an attack, for example to gain access to systems.

'Several combinations of social engineering' used during cyberattack on camera maker Axis

4.2 Criminals mix modi operandi as phishing and social engineering increase

The past 12 months have seen a further significant increase in phishing and social engineering. Facilitated by the ongoing pandemic, the number of COVID-19-related phishing attempts conducted across all via telephone (calling) and text messages (smishing) has risen considerably.

EUROPOL SOCTA 2021

RELEVANCE

Findings

- 26.2 billion of losses in 2020 with Business Email Compromise (BEC) attacks*
- 42.8% of all malicious attachments were Microsoft Office documents*
- 667% increase in phishing scores in only 1 month during the COVID-19 pandemic*
- 30% of phishing messages were delivered to inboxes*
- 32.5% of all the e-mails used the 'urgent' argument in the e-mail subject*

Cybercriminals Stole \$6.9 Billion In 2021, Using Social Engineering To Break Into Remote Workplaces

New research from Check Point Software finds social engineering is now a common attack strategy and organizations are getting hit frequently by hackers.

Social engineering attacks costly for business

By Alan Swartz and Senior Editor

HUMAN FACTOR IN CYBER SECURITY

- Encryption is getting stronger
- 2FA implemented by lots of service providers
- Technical cyber security measures keep improving
- Attack methods like brute forcing become less viable
- Human factor is still the weakest link in cyber security
- Social engineering attacks become more viable

TYPES OF SOCIAL ENGINEERING

- CEO-fraud
- Customer support scams /helpdesk fraud
- Nigerian prince scams
- Romance scams
- Cryptocurrency scams
- 'Friend in need fraud'
- Phishing

ATTACK VECTORS AND STRATEGIES

Umbrella term used for a wide variety of strategies and attack vectors.

TYPES OF SOCIAL ENGINEERING SPAM PHISHING

Non personalized , general message .

Casting a wide net.

Attempt to win trust (known company) and trigger a sense of urgency (account is blocked).

TYPES OF SOCIAL ENGINEERING SPEAR PHISHING

Specific person is targeted .

Tailored message based on job position and contacts .

High effort: requires specific information

Attempts to trigger a sense of urgency (deadline is tomorrow) , Assumes position of authority (CFD), win trust (same company)

MO change constantly and make use of actualities , like COVID or Ukraine conflict.

SETTING UP A PHISHING CAMPAINE IN FIVE STEPS

- Phishing kit
- Domain name
- Hosting service
- Install TLS certificate
- Send out Links

Acquired via Telegram | www.rabopas.nl | Abncheap | Free hosting | PostNL. Uw pakket heeft ons sortiecentrum bereikt. Volg de status via https://volgen.mypakketdienst.nl/info/PostNL

BIGPHISH AUTOMATICALLY SEARCH FOR PHISHING WEBSITES

BIGPHISH DEMO TIME!

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Ontwikkelaar phishing software opgepakt

Amstelveen - De politie heeft dinsdag een 26-jarige man uit Amstelveen aangehouden die een belangrijke faciliterende rol speelde bij phishing aanvallen. Het Landelijk Parket van het Openbaar Ministerie (OM) verdenkt de man van het ontwikkelen, voorhanden hebben en verspreiden van phishing panels. De panels zijn gericht op het verzamelen van inloggegevens van klanten van banken. De verdachte wordt vrijdag voorgeleid bij de rechter-commissaris in Rotterdam.

TNO

CYCLOPES Workshop sharing results on Social Engineering topic

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CYCLOPES Webinar WP2 Practitioner Workshop Results

24th May 2022
Meera Barnett
Shaun Mallinson
Anand Knox

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CONTENTS

- WP2 - Overview of Social Engineering workshop
- WP2 - Reflections on work delivered
 - Workshops
- WP2 – Dissemination of Results
 - Workshop findings
 - Reports

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Practitioner Workshops

DIGITAL FORENSICS: Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies

CYBERCRIME AFFECTING SYSTEMS: Cybercrime related to Remote Desktop Protocol

CYBERCRIME AFFECTING PEOPLE DIRECTLY: Social Engineering to Enable Cybercrime

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Practitioner Workshops – Attendance

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| Belgium Federal Police | NPCC Cybercrime Portfolio |
| Finland National Police Board | Riga State Police Regional Administration |
| Malta Ministry for Home Affairs | DS Cyber Prevent |
| Dutch National Police | GDOC |
| KWPG | City of London Police |
| Polish National Prosecutor's Office | Swedish Prosecution Authority |
| Guardia Civil | |

- Croatia Ministry of Interior
Swedish Police Authority
German Federal Criminal Police
Representatives from:
Kosovo
Ireland
Estonia

EU CONFIDENTIAL

Practitioner Workshops – Problem themes

- People
- Process
- Organisation
- Legal/Ethical
- Technical

People	Process	Organisation	Legal/Ethical	Technical
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising for law enforcement • Operational case awareness • Lack of equipment for online investigations • Lack of training from victims of actual programming due to mismanagement • Lack of trust in government • Lack of awareness of what is possible • Availability of low cost hardware 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of what is possible • Lack of equipment for online investigations • Lack of training from victims of actual programming due to mismanagement • Lack of trust in government • Lack of awareness of what is possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of equipment for online investigations • Lack of training from victims of actual programming due to mismanagement • Lack of trust in government • Lack of awareness of what is possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of equipment for online investigations • Lack of training from victims of actual programming due to mismanagement • Lack of trust in government • Lack of awareness of what is possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of equipment for online investigations • Lack of training from victims of actual programming due to mismanagement • Lack of trust in government • Lack of awareness of what is possible

WP2 – Reflections on Work Delivered

Successes, Challenges & Future Workshops

Successes	Challenges	Future Workshops
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to cover current capabilities, gaps and end-user needs in a fairly short space of time • Great engagement from participants • Fair representation from consortium partners • Community building • Different perspectives invaluable (e.g. Legal) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider representation useful • Timing – practitioner presentations and discussion sessions adding the most value • Theme setting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representation from WP1/2/3/4 at workshops • Look at wider tools for getting more representation from LEAs outside of the consortium • Workshop topic selection process

WP2 – Dissemination of Results

Workshop Results

Workshop Results

Sharing Workshop Results

- Reporting format
 - individual practitioners' workshop report (3 per year)
 - EC report (year 1)
- Dissemination event (20/21st April - Brussels)
 - main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders
 - ensure efficient cooperation between CYCLOPES and relevant partners
- Public facing reports
 - summary of topic and issues, practitioner priorities, and area of work and opportunities for development.

Best practice from a LEA practitioner

Cyber Prevent
Louise Gibson
DS Cyber Engagement

What is Cyber Prevent Objectives?

- To deter individuals from getting involved in cybercrime
- To understand human behaviours and motives behind cybercrime involvement
- To prevent reoffending

Cyber Prevent Subject

Anyone that has a high technical ability in computers and is either:

- is committing low-level cyber crime or,
- vulnerable to cyber criminal exploitation

is a subject for cyber choices.

Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime

Social Engineering has been use in some of our referrals which has identified gaps regarding our diversionary engagements

Case Study A

Case Study B

Social Engineering Gaps

- Law Enforcement Assumption- If social engineering used assumptions that have a lower technical ability
 - Training in social engineering for cyber staff to fully understand the subject
- Law Enforcement Ethics- Just completing work with subjects around CMA ethics is not effective with subjects have used social engineering
 - Morals and values have been included in our engagement pack to challenge some views around victim blaming identified.

Social Engineering Gaps

Long Term Behaviour Change- How do we change the behaviour long-term?
-Big challenge of law enforcement, how will this be measured?

Targeted messaging around social engineering- Making people aware of consequences.
Cyber Offender Risk Assessment.
-To include social engineering. Are they vulnerable to being social engineered and exploited by SOC

